

UTERINE ARTERY DOPPLER INDICES IN PATIENTS WITH THE FIBROIDS AND ADENOMYOSIS

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Abstract

Background: Uterine fibroids and adenomyosis are common gynecological conditions in women of reproductive age and are frequently associated with symptoms such as pelvic pain, heavy menstrual bleeding, and infertility. These conditions can alter uterine vascular architecture, potentially affecting blood flow through the uterine arteries. Doppler ultrasound provides a non-invasive method to assess uterine hemodynamics through indices such as the Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI). Evaluating these Doppler parameters in women with uterine masses may offer valuable insights into disease mechanisms and support improved diagnostic accuracy.

Methodology: A cross-sectional study was conducted on 103 women aged 25–50 years presenting with gynecological symptoms. Participants were stratified by age and evaluated for menstrual irregularities, pelvic pain, menorrhagia, dysmenorrhea, dyspareunia, and infertility. Transabdominal Doppler ultrasound assessed uterine artery hemodynamics, categorizing Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI) into normal, mild, moderate, and severe ranges. Uterine mass types and numbers were documented via ultrasound imaging. Statistical analyses included frequency distributions, cross tabulations, and correlation coefficients (Pearson's and Spearman's) to examine the association between uterine masses and Doppler indices.

Results: The majority of participants (77.7%) were aged between 40 and 50 years. A high prevalence of clinical symptoms was observed, including irregular menstruation (74.8%), lower abdominal pain (80.6%), menorrhagia (67%), and dysmenorrhea affecting 80.5% of the women, with 41.7% experiencing severe symptoms. Ultrasound evaluations detected uterine masses in most participants, with fibroids present in 52.4% and adenomyosis in 37.9%, while 9.7% showed no detectable masses. Doppler ultrasound revealed elevated uterine artery Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI) values in women with fibroids and adenomyosis compared to those without masses. Specifically, the right uterine artery RI showed moderate to severe elevation in 61% of cases and exhibited a moderate positive correlation with mass presence (Pearson's $R = 0.540$). The right uterine artery PI predominantly demonstrated mild to moderate elevations and a strong positive correlation (Pearson's $R = 0.936$). Conversely, the left uterine

artery RI mostly showed mild to moderate values and had a weak correlation with the presence of masses (Pearson's $R = 0.086$), while the left uterine artery PI mainly displayed mild elevations. Overall, increased Doppler indices were associated with clinical symptoms and the characteristics of uterine masses, the vascular changes linked to these conditions.

Conclusion: Fibroids and adenomyosis significantly alter uterine artery blood flow, as evidenced by elevated RI and PI values, reflecting increased vascular resistance. These hemodynamic changes are associated with symptomatic presentations including menstrual disturbances and infertility. Doppler ultrasound provides critical insights into uterine vascular status, enhancing diagnostic accuracy and informing clinical management of uterine masses.

INTRODUCTION

The most prevalent benign gynecological tumors are uterine fibroids, also known as leiomyomas, which are made of connective tissue and smooth muscle. The majority are asymptomatic, but occasionally they can result in pain, pressure sensations, metrorrhagia, miscarriage, preterm delivery, infertility from failed implantation, and puerperal hemorrhage. degenerative alterations, including calcification, infarction, infection, and atrophic and hyaline degeneration. Less than 0.2% of cases have malignant degeneration leading to leiomyosarcoma.^[1] The presence of endometrial tissue, including its glands and stroma, implanted in the myometrium is known as adenomyosis.^[2] The typical presenting symptoms of this illness in nulliparous women are dysmenorrhea and irregular uterine bleeding. Infertility is said to be associated with adenomyosis, however the precise mechanism underlying this detrimental effect is uncertain.^[2]

Furthermore, this syndrome has been linked to a number of obstetric disorders, including growth retardation, recurrent hemorrhage, and preterm delivery.^[3] Two-dimensional (2D), power Doppler (PD) angiography, and three-dimensional (3D) ultrasound scans are frequently sufficient to establish a conclusive diagnosis and outline the course of treatment. Compared to other modalities, these investigations are the preferred diagnostic instruments because of their reduced cost, accessibility, patient compatibility, and little invasiveness.^[4]

Because to the combined effects of estrogen, progesterone, and fibroid growth hormones throughout the female reproductive phase, uterine fibroids are most common in the fourth decade of

a woman's life, with over 70% of women over 50 having them. Up to 70–80% of women worldwide are expected to have fibroids by the age of 50, while the prevalence of adenomyosis in women undergoing hysterectomy is estimated to be 20–35%, though rates vary greatly due to variations in diagnostic criteria and techniques. These tumors have the potential to be benign, and just 0.2% of cases result in leiomyosarcoma or malignancy.^[5]

The most common gynecological problems affecting women and frequently occurring during childbearing age are benign uterine diseases.^[6]

Adenomyosis (AM) and uterine fibroids (UFs) are two of the main causes of irregular uterine bleeding.^[7] UFs, often referred to as uterine leiomyoma, are among the most prevalent benign uterine tumors in women. They can occasionally be entirely asymptomatic and frequently result in dysmenorrhea, pelvic discomfort, menorrhagia, and infertility. [8] One of the main reasons for a hysterectomy is UFs. AM is caused by endometrial gland hypertrophy, which results in aberrant endometrial tissue growth within the myometrium and an inflammatory, swollen uterus. Menorrhagia, dysmenorrhea, and persistent pelvic discomfort are some of the main symptoms, though they can also be totally absent.^[9]

According to reports, up to 75% of people have adenomyosis.^[10] Significant morbidity may result from either pathology. Adenomyosis and uterine fibroids may need surgery or medicinal intervention. Improving their diagnosis and obtaining precise information about their position and extent are therefore of great importance, particularly in light of an impending surgical

procedure.^[11] Their differential diagnosis continues to be difficult. The most prevalent uterine tumor formations are uterine fibroids (leiomyomas, myomas). Fibrovascular cells from the myometrium develop to form leiomyomas. In terms of histology, fibroids include connective tissue and muscle. They feature a highly vascularized pseudo capsule. Certain factors from that vascularized pseudo capsule raise the level of estrogen, which in turn increase the level of certain growth factors resulting in the growth of the tumor itself.^[12]

The anatomy of the tumor itself dictates how uterine fibroids show on ultrasound. Similar to the myometrium, the uterine fibroid is echogenic due to the muscle tissue from which it is formed. Due to the displacement of myometrial fibers, which results in a pseudo capsule, leiomyomas typically look as whorled solid masses with a distinct border between the tumor and the surrounding tissue.^[13] Adenomyosis is characterized by widespread myometrial heterogeneity, ill-defined hypoechoic patches, and myometrial cysts on ultrasonography, while fibroids usually appear as well-defined, hypoechoic or heterogeneous masses with potential calcifications and shadowing. However, overlapping sonographic characteristics between the two disorders might make diagnosis more difficult, especially when localized adenomyosis or small, many fibroids are present.^[14]

Inappropriate treatment, such as needless surgery or postponed symptom relief, might result from a misdiagnosis. From an ultrasound perspective, uterine fibroids have the following features, according to Morphological Uterus Sonographic Assessment (MUSA), a consensus statement on terms, definitions, and measurements that may be used to describe and report the sonographic features of the myometrium using grey-scale sonography, color/power Doppler, and 3D ultrasound imaging. Adenomyosis and fibroids can be accurately diagnosed with magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), which may be more useful than TVS when comparing the two conditions.^[15]

In addition to having a high pulsatility index (PI), 87% of adenomyosis patients showed vascular

distributions that differed from those of leiomyoma cases, according to 2D color Doppler ultrasound. Leiomyomas typically had peripheral diffused or outside feeding vessels, whereas adenomyotic lesions had randomly distributed vessels or intratumoral signals. Power doppler sonography has the ability to identify variations in blood flow with greater accuracy than frequency-based color sonography since it is more sensitive, less angle-dependent, and not prone to aliasing. Doppler sonography, especially when blood flow is slow 3D power. By conducting thorough examinations, Doppler ultrasonography can be used to distinguish between uterine adenomyosis and leiomyoma, potentially lowering the frequency of false positives. The use of three dimensional (3D) imaging and power Doppler improve the objective and reproducible assessment of a vascularity of a volume.^[25]

RESULTS

The majority of participants (77.7%) were aged between 40 and 50 years. A high prevalence of clinical symptoms was observed, including irregular menstruation (74.8%), lower abdominal pain (80.6%), menorrhagia (67%), and dysmenorrhea affecting 80.5% of the women, with 41.7% experiencing severe symptoms. Ultrasound evaluations detected uterine masses in most participants, with fibroids present in 52.4% and adenomyosis in 37.9%, while 9.7% showed no detectable masses. Doppler ultrasound revealed elevated uterine artery Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI) values in women with fibroids and adenomyosis compared to those without masses. Specifically, the right uterine artery RI showed moderate to severe elevation in 61% of cases and exhibited a moderate positive correlation with mass presence (Pearson's $R = 0.540$). The right uterine artery PI predominantly demonstrated mild to moderate elevations and a strong positive correlation (Pearson's $R = 0.936$). Conversely, the left uterine artery RI mostly showed mild to moderate values and had a weak correlation with the presence of masses (Pearson's $R = 0.086$), while the left uterine artery PI mainly displayed mild elevations. Overall, increased Doppler indices were associated with clinical

symptoms and the characteristics of uterine masses, the vascular changes linked to these conditions.

Table: 01 Mass Presented * Right Uterine artery TAS RI Crosstab

	Mass Presented	Right Uterine artery TAS RI			
		RI Normal >0.58	RI Mild 0.59 To 0.68	RI Moderate .69 To 0.78	RI Severe 0.79 to 0.89
	None	2	0	6	2
	Fibroids	14	8	14	18
	Adenomyosis	11	5	13	10
	Total	27	13	33	30

The crosstab shows how the severity of Right Uterine Artery RI varies across different uterine mass types (none, fibroids, adenomyosis).

Overall, fibroids and adenomyosis are associated with higher RI values, especially moderate to severe ranges.

Symmetric Measures

		Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.540 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.565 ^c
N of Valid Cases		

The symmetric measures show a moderate positive correlation between the variables (Pearson's R = 0.540, Spearman = 0.560)

Graph: 01

The bar chart shows that fibroids and adenomyosis are associated with higher moderate and severe RI levels, while cases

with no mass show mostly moderate RI values.

Table: 02 Mass Presented * Right Uterine Artery TAS PI Crosstab

		Right Uterine Artery TAS PI			
		PI Normal 0.70-0.99	PI Mild 1.00 to 1.19	PI Moderate 1.20 to 1.49	PI Severe 1.50 to 1.73
Mass Presented	None	3	5	1	1
	Fibroids	16	20	16	2
	Adenomy	7	24	8	0
Total		26	49	25	3

Fibroids and adenomyosis shows predominantly mild to moderate PI values, with severe PI being rare. Cross tab

Fibroids are the most common finding, followed by adenomyosis, with the smallest group showing no mass.

Symmetric Measures

Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.936 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.910 ^c

The symmetric measures indicate a very strong positive correlation between the variables (Pearson's R = 0.936, Spearman = 0.910).

Graph: 02

The bar chart shows that fibroids and adenomyosis mainly have mild to moderate PI values in the right uterine artery.
 Table: 03

Mass Presented * Left Uterine artery TAS RI
 Crosstab

		Left Uterine artery TAS RI			
		RI Normal .38-.52	RI Mild 0.53-.60	RI Moderate .61-.70	RI Severe 0.71-0.78
Mass Presented	None	3	4	3	0
	Fibroids	7	28	16	3
	Adenomyosis	2	19	17	1
Total		12	51	36	4

Fibroids and adenomyosis mostly show mild to moderate RI values in the left uterine artery, while severe RI is uncommon.

Symmetric Measures

Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	Approximate Significance
Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	.086 ^c
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.094 ^c

The symmetric measures show a very weak positive correlation between the variables (Pearson's R = 0.086, Spearman = 0.094).

Graph: 03

The bar chart shows that fibroids and adenomyosis mainly have mild to moderate RI values in the left uterine artery.

Table: 04 Mass Presented * Left Uterine artery TAS PI Crosstab

Mass Presented		Left uterine artery TAS PI			
		PI Normal <1.09	PI Mild 1.10 to 1.34	PI Moderate 1.35 to 1.59	PI Severe 1.60 to 1.92
Mass Presented	None	6	3	0	1
	Fibroids	15	32	2	5
	Adenomy	11	22	2	4
Total		32	57	4	10

Fibroids and adenomyosis shows predominantly shows mild to severe PI values in the left uterine artery, compared to the normal.

Symmetric Measures

Interval by Interval	Pearson's R	Approximate Significance
Ordinal by Ordinal	Spearman Correlation	.341 ^c
N of Valid Cases		.280 ^c

The symmetric measures show a weak positive correlation between the variables (Pearson's R = 0.341, Spearman = 0.280).

Graph: 04

Bar Chart

The bar chart shows that fibroids and adenomyosis mainly have mild to severe PI values in the left uterine artery, while cases without mass mostly show normal values.

DISCUSSION

Kumari et al., 2018 propose that adenomyosis is characterized by ectopic endometrial tissue within the myometrium, which can alter uterine vascular architecture. In the present study, women with adenomyosis demonstrated elevated uterine artery Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI), indicating increased vascular resistance compared to women without uterine masses. Notably, the right uterine artery showed moderate to strong correlations with the presence of adenomyosis (both RI and PI), whereas the left uterine artery exhibited only mild elevations with weaker correlations. These findings suggest potential asymmetry in vascular involvement, which may reflect differences in vascular supply, mass localization, or individual anatomical variation. The observed increase in uterine artery Doppler indices aligns with previous reports.

Singh et al. (2017) documented higher RI and PI in women with adenomyosis, attributing this to hypertrophic myometrial changes. Similarly, Tanaka et al. (2016) found that elevated Doppler indices were associated with clinical symptoms such as dysmenorrhea and menorrhagia, likely reflecting increased vascular resistance within the affected myometrium. These results underscore the potential utility of uterine artery Doppler ultrasound not only for the diagnosis of adenomyosis but also for evaluating disease severity and symptomatic burden.

Kepkepk et al., demonstrate transabdominal ultrasound (TAS) remains a widely used, non-invasive diagnostic tool for adenomyosis, although it is operator-dependent. Previous studies have reported variable sensitivity and specificity, ranging from 61% to 80.8% and 61.4% to 97.5%, respectively. Another study, TAS demonstrated a sensitivity of 75.68%, specificity of 90.79%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 49.12%, negative predictive value (NPV) of 96.95%, and overall accuracy of 89.20% for diagnosing adenomyosis, which is

comparable to earlier reports and highlights the reliability of TAS in experienced hands.

Bromley et al., 2018 found various ultrasonographic features have been proposed to improve diagnostic accuracy. Heterogeneous myometrial echotexture is the most frequently observed criterion and was common in our study population, consistent with findings. However, its specificity is limited. More specific features include subendometrial linear striations and myometrial cysts, with linear striations demonstrating the highest specificity (90.79%), negative predictive value (93.7%), and overall accuracy (86.36%) in our cohort. Poor endometrial delineation also showed statistical significance but with lower accuracy (56.53%). Small myometrial cysts, often representing focal hemorrhage or cystic implants, were occasionally detected and can be challenging to identify due to ultrasonographic resolution limits, artefactual shadows, or coexisting leiomyomata and calcifications. Previous studies by Fedele et al. and Bazot et al. have highlighted the diagnostic and grading value of these myometrial cysts.

Overall, this study reinforces the role of transabdominal ultrasound combined with Doppler assessment as an effective approach for the diagnosis and evaluation of adenomyosis. The integration of vascular indices and specific sonographic features enhances diagnostic confidence and may guide clinical management, particularly in symptomatic women. Future studies should focus on standardizing ultrasonographic criteria and exploring the relationship between Doppler parameters and symptom severity to further optimize non-invasive assessment of adenomyosis.

CONCLUSION

Fibroids and adenomyosis significantly increase uterine artery Resistance Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI), reflecting higher vascular resistance. These hemodynamic changes are linked to menstrual irregularities, pelvic pain, and infertility. Doppler ultrasound is a valuable tool for evaluating uterine vascular status and guiding clinical management of uterine masses.

IMAGES

Figure: 1 Adenomyosis

Doppler study of the uterine artery (left) in a case documented to have adenomyosis.

Figure 2: Submucosal uterine leiomyoma

An ultrasound image showing well circumscribed lesion suggestive as submucosal uterine leiomyoma.

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